

1 Expansion of Consistent Particle Method to Solve Solid Mechanics Problems

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6 SUMMARY

7 Originally developed for solving fluid dynamics problems, a Lagrangian particle
8 method called the Consistent Particle Method (CPM) is expanded to solid mechanics
9 problems in this paper. The motions of particles are governed by the mass conservation
10 and dynamics equations which are solved by the second-order predictor-corrector time
11 stepping scheme. The spatial derivatives of variables required in solving the governing
12 equations and computing strain increments are obtained by Taylor series expansion.
13 Stress components are updated from strain components according to the material
14 constitutive relation. The physical density of material is directly computed without
15 using particle number density. No additional particles are needed for the simulation of
16 boundaries. For boundary surface that is partially loaded, the Inverse Distance
17 Weighting method is applied to deal with the stress singularity problem due to sudden
18 change of stresses. Numerical examples including shock wave propagation and large
19 deformation of footing penetration are presented to demonstrate the capabilities of CPM
20 in solving solid mechanics problems.

21

22 KEY WORDS: particle method; Taylor series; solid mechanics; wave propagation;
23 footing penetration

24

25 1. INTRODUCTION

26 The Finite Element Method (FEM) has been widely used as the main numerical method
27 in solid mechanics. While it is matured and effective for solving small deformation
28 problems, there are challenges in solving large deformation problems, such as dealing
29 with severe element distortion which can lead to numerical inaccuracy or instability.
30 To tackle this problem, advanced techniques are required such as the Arbitrary
31 Lagrangian-Eulerian method [1, 2], Remeshing and Interpolation Technique by Small
32 Strain [3, 4], and Coupled Eulerian-Lagrangian method [5, 6]. These methods have their
33 respective advantages and disadvantages [7]. As a variant of FEM, the Particle Finite
34 Element Method (PFEM) uses a combination of elements and particles for solving large
35 deformation problems [8, 9]. To address the mesh distortion problem, remeshing based
36 on the positions of material particles is conducted at each step and the field variables
37 are transferred between elements and material particles in PFEM.

38 To avoid mesh related difficulties particularly for problems involving large
39 deformation, and moving boundary and interface, meshless (or meshfree) methods offer
40 an attractive alternative for solving solid and fluid dynamics problems by discretising
41 the continuum body with a set of particles or points. In the context of solid mechanics,
42 the Discrete Element Method [10] was proposed for simulating granular materials. The
43 Material Point Method [11] was proposed for modelling dynamic impact, penetration

44 as well as other large deformation problems. The Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics
45 (SPH) method is a particle method developed initially for astrophysical problems [12,
46 13] and has been extended to solve many other problems including solid mechanics [14,
47 15]. The SPH method defines a kernel function to approximate the Dirac delta function
48 in the computation of spatial derivatives of variables. The definition of kernel function
49 is not unique and can influence the computational results. On one hand, the kernel
50 function has to have a small influence domain in order to accurately approximate the
51 Dirac delta function (which is zero everywhere except at a point). On the other hand,
52 the influence domain has to contain sufficient particles for good numerical accuracy.
53 These two contradicting requirements are not always possible to meet, particularly if
54 particles undergo large displacements. A common consequence is the spurious
55 fluctuation in stress or pressure time history. To alleviate this problem, empirical
56 stabilisation terms (e.g. artificial viscosity/damping) or error compensation terms [15,
57 16] are often used. Another particle method, known as the Moving Particle Semi-
58 implicit (MPS) method [17, 18] has been used for fluid mechanics problems and more
59 recently for solid mechanics problems [19, 20]. The accuracy of MPS depends on the
60 choice of weighting function used to approximate the derivatives of variables.
61 According to Souto-Iglesias *et al.* [21], the weighting functions in MPS are in fact
62 equivalent to the kernel functions in SPH. Comprehensive reviews of meshless methods
63 can be found in Belytschko *et al.* [22] and Luo *et al.* [23].

64 A Lagrangian particle method called the Consistent Particle Method (CPM) was
65 proposed for solving fluid dynamics problems [24, 25], fluid-structure interaction [26],

66 water-air interaction [27, 28], and submarine landslide by treating soil particle
67 movement as fluid flow [29, 30]. CPM solves the Navier-Stokes equations which
68 govern the motion of particles by using a predictor-corrector method as the time
69 stepping scheme. For the computation of the spatial derivatives of variables, Taylor
70 series expansion with second-order accuracy is applied, instead of using a kernel
71 function. Notably no artificial damping or stabilisation term is needed in CPM, while
72 the computational time of CPM is similar to that of other particle methods. Nevertheless,
73 CPM has thus far not been developed to solve solid mechanics problems. Taking
74 advantage of its direct use of Taylor series in computing spatial derivatives, this study
75 expands CPM to the domain of solid mechanics with focus on wave propagation and
76 penetration of strip footing in soil continuum.

77 In applying particle methods to solid mechanics problems, there are two main
78 differences from solving fluid dynamics problems. The constitutive relations for solid
79 involve stress and strain tensors, which are more complicated than computing scalar
80 pressure in fluid dynamics problems, this may involve stress update for nonlinear
81 materials. Application of stress boundary conditions is also more complicated. For
82 example, at the free surface, not all components of the stress vector are zero for solid
83 whereas pressure (scalar) is zero for fluid.

84 2. CONSISTENT PARTICLE METHOD FOR SOLID MECHANICS PROBLEMS

85 2.1. *Predictor-Corrector procedure*

86 In particle methods, the solid domain is discretised by a set of particles governed by the
87 mass conservation and dynamics (momentum) equations as shown below

88
$$\frac{d\rho}{dt} = -\rho \frac{\partial v^\alpha}{\partial x^\alpha} \quad (1)$$

89
$$\frac{dv^\alpha}{dt} = \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial \sigma^{\alpha\beta}}{\partial x^\beta} + a^\alpha - \mu v^\alpha \quad (2)$$

90 where Einstein notation is applied with α and β denoting the components of Cartesian
 91 coordinate system, ρ is material density, t is time, v is velocity, x is spatial coordinate,
 92 σ is stress, a is acceleration due to body force, and μ is material damping coefficient.

93 Predictor step: Based on the solutions at the n -th time step, Euler's method is used
 94 to obtain the "predicted" velocities and coordinates at the next step as follows:

95
$$\left(v_{n+1}^\alpha\right)_p = v_n^\alpha + \Delta t \frac{dv_n^\alpha}{dt} \quad (3)$$

96
$$\left(x_{n+1}^\alpha\right)_p = x_n^\alpha + \Delta t \left(v_{n+1}^\alpha\right)_p \quad (4)$$

97 The strain increments are calculated by using the predicted velocities and coordinates:

98
$$\left(\Delta \varepsilon_{n+1}^{\alpha\beta}\right)_p = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \left(v_{n+1}^\alpha\right)_p}{\partial \left(x_{n+1}^\beta\right)_p} + \frac{\partial \left(v_{n+1}^\beta\right)_p}{\partial \left(x_{n+1}^\alpha\right)_p} \right) \Delta t \quad (5)$$

99 where the spatial derivatives of velocities are determined by Taylor series expansion
 100 (see Section 2.2). The predicted stress increments of each particle, $\left(\Delta \sigma_{n+1}^{\alpha\beta}\right)_p$, are
 101 obtained through the material constitutive equations to update the predicted stresses:

102
$$\left(\sigma_{n+1}^{\alpha\beta}\right)_p = \sigma_n^{\alpha\beta} + \left(\Delta \sigma_{n+1}^{\alpha\beta}\right)_p \quad (6)$$

103 Note that the material density (if changed) is computed using Equation (1) for its
 104 physical value, and it is not necessary to use particle number density as a proxy which
 105 is commonly adopted in particle methods for fluid dynamics, as shown below.

$$106 \quad (\rho_{n+1})_p = \rho_n \left(1 - \frac{\partial (v_{n+1}^\alpha)_p}{\partial (x_{n+1}^\alpha)_p} \Delta t \right) \quad (7)$$

107 Using the above results obtained from Equations (6) and (7), the predicted acceleration
 108 can be calculated by using Equation (2):

$$109 \quad \frac{d(v_{n+1}^\alpha)_p}{dt} = \frac{1}{(\rho_{n+1})_p} \frac{\partial (\sigma_{n+1}^{\alpha\beta})_p}{\partial (x_{n+1}^\beta)_p} + a_{n+1}^\alpha \quad (8)$$

110 where the spatial derivatives of stress components are also determined by Taylor series
 111 expansion.

112 Corrector step: The predicted values of velocities, coordinates, stresses and density
 113 of particles are used to compute the “corrected” values at t_{n+1} based on the trapezoidal
 114 method, as follows:

$$115 \quad v_{n+1}^\alpha = v_n^\alpha + \frac{\Delta t}{2} \left[\frac{d(v_{n+1}^\alpha)_p}{dt} + \frac{dv_n^\alpha}{dt} \right] \quad (9)$$

$$116 \quad x_{n+1}^\alpha = x_n^\alpha + \Delta t v_{n+1}^\alpha \quad (10)$$

$$117 \quad \Delta \varepsilon_{n+1}^{\alpha\beta} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial v_{n+1}^\alpha}{\partial x_{n+1}^\beta} + \frac{\partial v_{n+1}^\beta}{\partial x_{n+1}^\alpha} \right) \Delta t \quad (11)$$

118 The corrected stress increments, $\Delta\sigma_{n+1}^{\alpha\beta}$, are computed from the material constitutive
 119 law to update the corrected total stresses and density of particles as follows:

$$120 \quad \sigma_{n+1}^{\alpha\beta} = \sigma_n^{\alpha\beta} + \Delta\sigma_{n+1}^{\alpha\beta} \quad (12)$$

$$121 \quad \rho_{n+1} = \rho_n \left(1 - \frac{\partial v_{n+1}^\alpha}{\partial x_{n+1}^\alpha} \Delta t \right) \quad (13)$$

122 The above predictor-corrector procedure is schematically shown in Figure 1 and is
 123 repeated for each time step until the required time duration is completed. For numerical
 124 stability, the time step (Δt) has to satisfy Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy (CFL) condition as
 125 follows [31]:

$$126 \quad C = \frac{V_w \Delta t}{L_p} \leq 1 \quad (14)$$

127 where C is known as Courant number, L_p is the distance between particles, and V_w is
 128 the wave speed of material. Courant number of 0.2 (unless otherwise stated) is used
 129 herein to provide a sufficient stability margin and good accuracy.

130 2.2. Computation of spatial derivatives by Taylor series

131 Consider a differentiable function f in a two-dimensional (2D) space. Its value at a point
 132 (x_j, y_j) can be expanded as a Taylor series about a reference point (x_i, y_i) as follows:

$$133 \quad f_j = f(x_j, y_j) = f_i + hf_{,xi} + kf_{,yi} + \frac{1}{2}h^2 f_{,xxi} + hkf_{,xyi} + \frac{1}{2}k^2 f_{,yyi} + O(r^3) \quad (15)$$

134 where $h = x_j - x_i$, $k = y_j - y_i$, a comma in subscript denotes partial derivative with
 135 respect to the coordinate, $O(r^3)$ represents the truncation error of third order with

$$136 \quad r = \sqrt{h^2 + k^2} .$$

137 Taylor series expansion is applied to a sufficient number of neighbour particles ($j =$
138 $1, \dots, N$) within an influence radius r_e as shown in Figure 2. Given the coordinates of
139 the reference particle i and neighbour particles j and their values of a specific variable
140 (be it velocity, stress or density), the first-order and second-order spatial derivatives of
141 the variable at particle i can be calculated by solving a set of linear equations [24]. Since
142 there are five unknown derivatives (i.e. $f_{,xi}$, $f_{,yi}$, $f_{,xxi}$, $f_{,xyi}$ and $f_{,yyi}$) for 2D problems,
143 minimally five neighbour particles would suffice. Nevertheless using more neighbour
144 particles will improve the accuracy of calculation, leading to an over-determined
145 system of linear equations which is solved by the weighted least square method [24,
146 32]. The weight is inversly proportional to the cube of distance and is therefore
147 consistent with the third-order truncation error in Taylor series expansion in Equation
148 (15).

149 To ensure that there are always at least five neighbour particles for all particles,
150 including particles at the corner area of the simulation domain, the value of influence
151 radius r_e is chosen to be $3.1L_0$ as shown in Figure 2, where L_0 is the initial particle
152 spacing. Note that, by using Taylor series expansion, CPM does not require the full
153 influence circle to be within the solid domain (as long as there are at least five neighbour
154 particles). Thus all particles used are in the physical material domain and there is no
155 needed for additional particles such as mirror or ghost particles outside the boundary.
156 For the selection of neighbour particles, the candidate list method proposed by
157 Koshizuka *et al.* [33] adopted here due to its computational efficiency as shown in a
158 sensitivy study by Viccione *et al.* [34].

159 *2.3. Boundary conditions*

160 For particle methods, imposing boundary conditions is generally less straightforward
161 than mesh-based methods. In kernel-based particle methods, truncation of kernel
162 function (which has a requirement of symmetry) near boundaries can give rise to
163 consistency and convergence issues [35]. Additional particles, such as mirror and ghost
164 particles, are often added outside the boundaries [36, 37]. Nevertheless, the
165 determination of positions and parameters for these additional particles can be
166 complicated especially when the boundary is of irregular shape or moving. In this study,
167 since kernel function is not used, additional particles are not needed and this offers a
168 considerable advantage from the viewpoint of numerical implementation. Velocity and
169 stress boundary conditions are directly assigned to boundary particles – including the
170 free surface boundary condition.

171 If a boundary is subjected to a strip or patch load, the direct assignment of stress
172 components does not work well at the edge of the applied load where stress singularity
173 exists due to the abrupt change of stresses [38]. An example is soil settlement under a
174 rigid strip footing which causes a non-zero applied stress under the footing. But the
175 vertical stress is zero on the free surface immediately outside the edge of footing. If a
176 particle is located at the edge of footing, its vertical stress is mathematically undefined
177 (between the applied stress and zero value) and cannot be assigned directly as a
178 boundary condition. In this context, the method of Inverse Distance Weighting (IDW),
179 originally used for panel load approximation [39], is adopted in this study. The idea is
180 to compute the value of an unknown at a position by the distance-weighted average of

181 the values at other positions. Nevertheless, Meddaikar *et al.* [39] used all the quantities
 182 in the whole domain in the IDW method, and this approach is time-consuming. Here,
 183 the IDW method is only applied to free surface particles when there is stress singularity,
 184 based on the values at the neighbour particles within the influence radius ($r_e = 3.1L_0$).
 185 In this way, the computation is localised and efficient as only a small number of
 186 neighbour particles are used. In addition, only real (material) particles are used, thereby
 187 avoiding the complexities of generating mirror particles. Accordingly, stress and
 188 velocity components at particle i near stress singularity are given by

$$189 \quad \sigma_i^{\alpha\beta} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^N \sigma_j^{\alpha\beta} w_{ij}}{\sum_{j=1}^N w_{ij}} \quad (16)$$

$$190 \quad v_i^\alpha = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^N v_j^\alpha w_{ij}}{\sum_{j=1}^N w_{ij}} \quad (17)$$

191 Note that the distance-weighting function $w_{ij} = 1/r_{ij}^3$ is defined to be consistent with the
 192 local truncation error of Taylor series expansion, where r_{ij} is the distance between the
 193 reference particle i and neighbour particle j within the influence radius.

194 2.4. Material damping

195 In CPM, no artificial damping or viscosity is needed. If material damping is to be
 196 accounted for, mass proportional damping is used [40]. The material damping
 197 coefficient in Equation (2) is obtained as $\mu = 2\zeta\omega$ where ζ is the damping ratio and ω is
 198 the fundamental frequency.

199 *2.5. Particle repositioning and removal*

200 For large deformation problems, particle displacements can be significant to cause
201 highly irregular particle distribution and adversely affect the numerical performance of
202 particle methods. A simple “particle repositioning” scheme is proposed in this study to
203 redefine the particle positions so as to achieve a more regular particle spacing.
204 Furthermore, when particles are too densely distributed, some particles become
205 redundant (for numerical accuracy) and can be removed by a proposed “particle
206 removal” scheme. Both the particle repositioning scheme and particle removal scheme
207 are explained in Appendix A.

208 **3. NUMERICAL EXAMPLES AND DISCUSSIONS**

209 To verify the feasibility and accuracy of CPM for solving solid mechanics problems,
210 five numerical examples as summarised in Table 1 are presented to compare with the
211 results obtained by other methods.

212 *3.1. Shock wave in a metal rod under compressive stress*

213 The first example is 1D shock wave propagation in an undamped elastic magnesium
214 rod previously studied by He [41] using SPH. As shown in Figure 3, the right end of
215 the rod is fixed and the left end is excited by a compressive stress $\sigma_{applied} = 8.8436$ MPa
216 suddenly at time $t = 0$. The parameters of the rod are: length $L = 1$ m, cross sectional
217 area $A = 100$ mm², Young’s modulus $E = 45$ GPa and density $\rho = 1738$ kg/m³. The
218 analytical velocity solution (He, 2015) is $v = \sigma_{applied}/\sqrt{\rho E} = 1$ m/s, and the wave
219 propagates along the rod at a speed of $V_w = \sqrt{E/\rho} = 5088.4$ m/s.

220 Particles in a straight line are used to model the rod in CPM. The right end particle
221 is assigned a zero velocity and the left end particle is assigned the applied stress. For
222 comparison with the analytical undamped solution, no damping (material or artificial)
223 is used in CPM. Based on 251 particles, the CPM results are compared with the SPH
224 results (also 251 particles but with artificial viscosity) that used four different time
225 stepping schemes, namely, the first-order Euler scheme, second-order predictor-
226 corrector (PC2) scheme, fourth-order Runge-Kutta (RK4) scheme and second-order
227 Runge-Kutta-Chebyshev (RKC) scheme. The same time step as that used in He [41] is
228 adopted here: $\Delta t = CL_0/V_w = 0.47 \mu\text{s}$, where Courant number C is 0.6 and L_0 is the initial
229 particle spacing. As shown in Figures 4 and 5 for velocity distribution and stress history,
230 respectively, the CPM results are much closer to the analytical solutions [41] than the
231 SPH results with four different time stepping schemes (including the high-order RK4
232 scheme). Figure 6 compares the CPM results with the best SPH results based on RKC
233 scheme using 251, 1,001 and 10,001 particles ($\Delta t = 0.47, 0.12$ and $0.012 \mu\text{s}$
234 respectively). The CPM result using 1,001 particles is as good as the RKC-SPH result
235 using 10,001 particles, and the CPM result using 10,001 particles are nearly identical
236 to the analytical solution of shock wave.

237 *3.2. Wave propagation in a rectangular plate under tensile stress*

238 In the second example, a rectangular steel plate of 0.2 m length and 0.1 m width is
239 constrained on the left side as shown in Figure 7. A uniform tensile stress $\sigma_{applied} = 150$
240 MPa is suddenly applied at $t = 0$ on the right side. The top and bottom sides are free
241 surfaces. Young's modulus is $E = 200 \text{ GPa}$, density is $\rho = 7800 \text{ kg/m}^3$ and Poisson's

242 ratio is $\nu = 0.3$. The primary wave speed is $V_p = \sqrt{E(1-\nu)/[\rho(1-\nu-2\nu^2)]} = 5875.1$
243 m/s which is used as the wave speed to determine the time step $\Delta t = CL_0/V_p$, where C
244 = 0.2.

245 This 2D plane stress problem was first studied in a FEM study by Swaddiwudhipong
246 and Liu [42] using eight $50 \text{ mm} \times 50 \text{ mm}$ quadratic shell elements (45 nodes in total)
247 and a time step of $1 \mu\text{s}$. It was then studied by Liu *et al.* [43] using the SPH method
248 with artificial viscosity and three different numbers of particles: model 1 with 51×26
249 particles, model 2 with 101×51 particles and model 3 with 201×101 particles. The
250 SPH study adopted the leap-frog time stepping scheme with second-order accuracy,
251 and the time steps were $0.4 \mu\text{s}$, $0.2 \mu\text{s}$ and $0.1 \mu\text{s}$ for models 1, 2 and 3 respectively.
252 When the continuum is stretched under tensile stress, tensile instability problem may
253 arise in which the motions of particles may become unstable [44]. This problem is
254 related to the selection of kernel function and requires special treatment [45]. In the
255 SPH study by Liu *et al.* [43], even with additional stress points added to tackle the
256 tensile instability problem, SPH model 1 (51×26 particles) is not acceptable as the
257 results oscillate severely. But SPH model 2 and model 3 give similar results indicating
258 convergence.

259 The CPM simulation is conducted with two models, i.e. model 1 with 51×26
260 particles (see Figure 8) and model 2 with 101×51 particles. The respective time steps
261 are $0.4 \mu\text{s}$ and $0.2 \mu\text{s}$, the same as in the SPH study. The top and bottom free surfaces
262 are simulated by directly assigning $\sigma_{yy} = \sigma_{xy} = 0$ to free surface particles. Particles along
263 the sliding boundary are assigned $v_x = 0$ and $\sigma_{xy} = 0$, and particles along the loaded

264 boundary are assigned $\sigma_{xx} = 150$ MPa from $t = 0$ onwards. The results at three points (A,
265 B and C) as shown in Figure 8 are obtained and compared with the FEM results [42]
266 and the SPH results [43]. Figures 9 and 10 show the horizontal displacement results at
267 points B and C respectively, whereas Figures 11 and 12 show the horizontal stress (σ_{xx})
268 results at points A and B respectively. It is shown that the CPM results using only $51 \times$
269 26 particles are very similar to the SPH results using more particles (101×51 particles),
270 and are in good agreement with the FEM results. No damping (real or artificial) is used
271 in the CPM simulation. In addition, CPM does not encounter tensile instability problem
272 and thus no special treatment is needed when the stress state is in tension.

273 *3.3. Loading, unloading and reloading of soil under reversing velocity*

274 In the third example, a 2D plane strain problem of soil compression with loading,
275 unloading and reloading is studied as shown in Figure 13. The soil domain is of
276 dimensions $L = d = 1$ m with the bottom boundary fixed and the two vertical boundaries
277 sliding. The top boundary moves vertically at a prescribed velocity with change of sign
278 in the time history. The soil parameters are: Young's modulus = 50 MPa, density =
279 2000 kg/m^3 and Poisson's ratio = 0.3. The primary wave speed in the soil is 183.4 m/s
280 for determining the time step $\Delta t = CL_0/V_p$, where $C = 0.2$.

281 A symmetric boundary is imposed along the vertical centre line by assigning $v_x = 0$
282 and $\sigma_{xy} = 0$ along the boundary, and only the right half of the soil domain is studied.
283 The CPM model uses 81×161 particles with $\Delta t = 6.8 \mu\text{s}$. Particles at the bottom fixed
284 boundary are assigned $v_x = v_y = 0$, and particles at the right sliding boundary are
285 assigned $v_x = 0$ and $\sigma_{xy} = 0$. The top boundary particles are assigned the prescribed

286 vertical velocity as shown in Figure 13 and zero horizontal velocity. For comparison,
287 FEM results are obtained by explicit dynamic analysis with 80×160 four-node
288 elements (13041 nodes in total) and $\Delta t = 6.8 \mu\text{s}$ using Abaqus software [46]. To
289 represent real material, mass proportional damping is used with 5% damping ratio.

290 Two elastic-perfectly plastic models are considered using: (A) von Mises (inscribed)
291 failure criterion with undrained shear strength $c_u = 100 \text{ kPa}$ and (B) inscribed Drucker-
292 Prager failure criterion with associated flow rule, cohesion $c = 100 \text{ kPa}$, friction angle
293 $\varphi = 20^\circ$ and dilation angle $\psi = 20^\circ$. The explicit integration method [47] is used to update
294 stresses. To show the behaviour of loading, unloading and reloading, the vertical stress
295 at the midpoint of top boundary is plotted against the vertical displacement at the same
296 point. For both von Mises and Drucker-Prager models, the CPM results are in excellent
297 agreement with the FEM results as shown in Figures 14 and 15 respectively (herein
298 compression is taken as positive which is common in geotechnical engineering).

299 *3.4. Bearing capacity of rigid strip footing on soil stratum*

300 The fourth example aims to obtain the bearing capacity of a rigid strip on a soil stratum,
301 which was previously studied by Bui and Khoa [48] using SPH with leapfrog time
302 stepping method. As shown in Figure 16, the horizontal and vertical dimensions of the
303 plane strain model are $L = 20 \text{ m}$ and $d = 3.66 \text{ m}$, respectively. The width of the rigid
304 rough (non-slip) strip footing is $B = 3.14 \text{ m}$. Only the right half domain is analysed with
305 symmetric boundary condition ($v_x = 0, \sigma_{xy} = 0$). The bottom boundary is fixed ($v_x = v_y$
306 $= 0$), and the right boundary is sliding ($v_x = 0, \sigma_{xy} = 0$). A prescribed vertical velocity
307 shown in Figure 16 and zero horizontal velocity are imposed on the soil particles

308 beneath the rough footing. The IDW method as explained earlier is applied to the
309 particles on free surface to tackle the problem of stress singularity near the edge of
310 footing.

311 The soil parameters are: Young's modulus $E = 207$ MPa, density $\rho = 2650$ kg/m³,
312 Poisson's ratio $\nu = 0.3$, cohesion $c = 69$ kPa and friction angle $\phi = 20^\circ$. Drucker-Prager
313 model is used with two flow rules: (A) associated flow rule with both friction angle (ϕ)
314 and dilation angle (ψ) equal to 20° , and (B) non-associated flow rule with $\phi = 20^\circ$ and
315 $\psi = 0^\circ$.

316 In the CPM model, 137×51 particles are used with the initial particle spacing of
317 0.0732 m – the same as that used in SPH by Bui and Khoa [48]. For comparison, the
318 FEM simulation using Abaqus explicit dynamic analysis is conducted using 136×50
319 four-node elements (6987 nodes in total). A time step of 45.1 μ s and material damping
320 ratio of 5% are used in both CPM and FEM simulations.

321 Case A: Associated flow rule with friction and dilation angles equal to 20°

322 The bearing curves obtained by CPM, FEM (Abaqus) and SPH [48] are compared in
323 Figure 17 for Drucker-Prager model with associated flow rule ($\phi = \psi = 20^\circ$). The CPM
324 result is very close to the FEM result, but there is a discrepancy between the SPH result
325 and FEM result. In the initial settlement of up to about 2 cm, the pressure-settlement
326 relationship is approximately linear with slight softening. As the footing moves further
327 down, it pushes an increasing volume of soil beneath and around the footing downward
328 and sideways (due to Poisson's effect). When a significant portion of the soil domain
329 under high compression goes into plastic zone, the softening behaviour becomes severe

330 and approaches the bearing capacity. In this case of Drucker-Prager model with dilation
331 angle of 20° , the dilation (expansion) of soil is resisted by the confining pressure of
332 surrounding soil, which contributes to slight increase in resistance to the footing
333 settlement. Hence the averaged pressure continues to increase with increasing footing
334 settlement, albeit at a slow rate.

335 Case B: Non-associated flow rule with friction angle of 20° and zero dilation angle

336 For Drucker-Prager model with non-associated flow rule ($\varphi = 20^\circ$ and $\psi = 0^\circ$), there is
337 no dilation effect and thus the average pressure reaches an approximately constant value
338 as shown in Figure 18. The CPM result is in very good agreement with both FEM result
339 and SPH result. If the footing continues to move downward, the footing settlement
340 problem will turn into a footing penetration problem with development of slip surface
341 which will be presented in the next example.

342 *3.5. Penetration of rigid strip footing in soil stratum*

343 Finally, strip footing penetration in soil stratum of undrained clay is studied for two
344 different penetration depths.

345 Case (A): Penetration of rigid strip footing for $D = 0.25B$

346 Consider a footing penetration problem in which a rigid rough strip footing penetrates
347 in soil stratum to a depth D that is 0.25 times of the footing width B . The 2D plain strain
348 problem was previously studied by FEM [49] (using implicit and explicit integration
349 schemes as well as Coupled Eulerian-Lagrangian (CEL) approach in Abaqus) and
350 Strain-smoothed Particle Finite Element Method (SPFEM) [50]. As shown in Figure
351 19, the soil stratum is of dimensions $L = d = 4$ m. The footing width is $B = 2$ m and its

352 thickness is negligible. Soil material is simulated using von Mises (inscribed) model
353 with Young's modulus of 1 MPa, density 1600 kg/m³, Poisson's ratio 0.49 and
354 undrained shear strength 10 kPa. The time step is determined by $\Delta t = CL_0/V_p$ with
355 Courant number $C = 0.2$ and primary wave speed of 103.4 m/s. Mass proportional
356 damping with 5% damping ratio is used to account for material damping in the study.

357 A symmetric boundary is applied along the vertical centre line and only the right half
358 is modelled. The bottom boundary is fixed and the right boundary is sliding. The top
359 boundary particles at the bottom of footing are subjected to a vertical velocity of 0.01
360 m/s from $t = 0$ onwards. When the footing penetration is substantial, a nearly vertical
361 free surface of soil emerges near the footing edge. The IDW method is applied to free
362 surface particles near the footing edge, accounting for changes in the inclination of
363 these free surfaces (which are not necessarily vertical or horizontal during deformation).

364 After a convergence study, it is found sufficient to use 33×65 particles ($\Delta t = 0.12$
365 ms) to simulate the right half of the domain. As the penetration depth of footing
366 increases, the soil particle distribution near the edge of footing gradually becomes
367 irregular. This is because the soil beneath the footing is compressed downward
368 (particles become denser) while the soil outside the footing heaves upward (particles
369 become looser). To tackle this problem, the proposed scheme of particle repositioning
370 as explained in Appendix A is used to adjust the particle positions. For ease of
371 implementation, this scheme is applied to all particles at each time step since it does
372 not significantly increase the computational time. Note that the particle repositioning
373 scheme does not move the particles to the new positions. Instead, it reselects a set of

374 new particles (to replace the old particles) with their velocities, stresses and density
375 computed based on Taylor series expansion (see Appendix A).

376 Based on the slip line theory [51], the analytical solution of the average pressure on
377 footing is $p = (2 + \pi) c_u$ when $B/L = 0.5$. Figure 20 compares the bearing capacity results
378 obtained by CPM, FEM [49], SPFEM [50] and the analytical solution [51]. The bearing
379 curves in the figure are plotted in terms of the normalised resistance force $V/(Bc_u)$
380 against the normalised penetration depth D/B . The bearing curve obtained by CPM
381 agrees very well with the analytical solution, whereas the FEM and SPFEM results
382 show larger resistance force than the analytical solution. Figure 21 shows the CPM
383 particle distribution at $D = 0.25B$. It can be seen that the heave-up volume of soil is
384 about the same as the volume of soil displaced by the downward movement of footing,
385 and this is explained by the nearly incompressible soil with Poisson's ratio of 0.49.
386 Figure 22 shows similar soil profiles near the top boundary obtained by various
387 numerical methods, except for FEM that uses the explicit integration scheme. Figure
388 23 plots the velocity vectors and show the slip surface that demarcates the moving soil
389 above it and non-moving soil below it.

390 Case (B): Penetration of rigid strip footing for $D = 2.0B$

391 Another problem of penetration of rigid strip footing in soil is studied – with a large
392 penetration depth which is two times of the footing width. As shown in Figure 24, the
393 dimensions of the soil stratum are $L = 12$ m and $d = 4$ m, and the footing width is $B =$
394 1 m. The soil stratum is modelled as a von Mises (circumscribed) material with Young's
395 modulus of 100 kPa, density 2000 kg/m³, Poisson's ratio 0.49 and undrained shear

396 strength 1 kPa. The time step is determined by $\Delta t = CL_0/V_p$, where $C = 0.2$ and $V_p =$
397 29.3 m/s. Mass proportional damping with a damping ratio of 5% is used as material
398 damping. The boundary conditions are applied the same way as the previous problem
399 of $D = 0.25B$, except that the applied velocity on the top boundary particles at the
400 footing is different as given in Figure 24.

401 In the CPM simulation, 97×65 particles are used to model the right half of the soil
402 domain ($\Delta t = 0.43$ ms). The particle repositioning scheme is applied to all particles at
403 each time step to pre-empt highly irregular particle distribution. In addition, due to the
404 large penetration depth, the soil below the footing is highly compressed resulting in
405 considerable decrease in the vertical particle spacing. The particle removal scheme as
406 described in Appendix A is therefore applied by removing some particles near the
407 bottom boundary in the compression zone. Note that for solid mechanics problems,
408 CPM computes physical density of material directly and not particle number density.
409 Hence, the removal of particles is straightforward since there is no need to re-compute
410 particle number density arising from the reduction in number of particles.

411 For verification, the Remeshing and Interpolation Technique by Small Strain (RITSS)
412 method is used based on 72×48 four-node elements (Kencana, 2021), and damping is
413 not involved as RITSS uses static analysis. Figure 25 shows the normalised resistance
414 force $V/(Bc_u)$ versus the normalised penetration D/B . The CPM result shows better
415 stability than the RITSS result which has significant fluctuations. Furthermore, the
416 RITSS result shows a larger resistance because the linear quadrilateral elements used
417 in RITSS is of first-order accuracy which makes the elements stiffer than in actuality.

418 In Figures 26, the CPM particle distribution at $D = 2.0B$ displays large deformation of
419 soil caused by footing penetration, including large heave caused by sideward movement
420 of soil displaced by footing penetration. The soil profiles obtained by CPM and RITSS
421 are compared in Figure 27. Note that the change in soil volume is expected to be
422 negligible since Poisson's ratio of soil is 0.49. Hence, a deep penetration is expected to
423 cause a large heave which is captured by CPM but not RITSS. Figure 28 shows the
424 velocity vectors and the slip surface obtained by CPM at $D = 2.0B$.

425 5. CONCLUSIONS

426 Originally developed for fluid dynamics problems, the Consistent Particle Method is
427 expanded to solve solid mechanics problems. As it does not use kernel function, it
428 eliminates the problems associated with kernel truncation problem and thus does not
429 need ghost or mirror particles near the boundary. Of noteworthy is that CPM does not
430 need artificial damping/viscosity other than physical damping of material if present.
431 Also, material density is directly computed as part of the solution without the use of
432 particle number density. The IDW method is applied to boundary particles at free
433 surface near applied loading where stress singularity arises from abrupt change of
434 stresses. Two simple schemes of particle repositioning and particle removal are
435 proposed to avoid highly irregular particle distribution that can cause numerical
436 inaccuracy. The good performance of CPM in terms of accuracy and stability for solid
437 mechanics problems has been demonstrated by numerical examples covering shock
438 wave propagation problems as well as bearing capacity and large-deformation
439 penetration of footing in nonlinear soil stratum.

440 APPENDIX A

441 *A.1. Particle repositioning scheme*

442 Large deformation may result in highly irregular particle distribution and potentially
443 degrade numerical accuracy. In the proposed particle repositioning scheme, the
444 irregularly distributed “old” particles is replaced by a set of more regularly distributed
445 “new” particles in two steps: (a) determination of positions of new particles and (b)
446 computation of variables of new particles based on Taylor series expansion.

447 The position of a new particle i' , which replaces an old particle i , is determined by
448 averaging the coordinates of pairs of old particles selected from the neighbour particles.
449 To select these paired neighbour particles, a circular domain with radius $1.7L_0$ centred
450 at the old particle i is used as shown in Figure A.1. The circular domain is evenly
451 divided into eight sectors. If the number of particles in two diametrically opposite
452 sectors are the same, these particles will be selected for the determination of the position
453 of new particle i' . Otherwise, they will not be selected. For illustration in Figure A.1,
454 two particles j_1 and j_2 in two diametrically opposite sectors are a pair of particles
455 selected for determining the position of new particle i' . Similarly, four particles j_3 to j_6
456 in two diametrically opposite sectors are also selected. The new particle position is
457 simply obtained by averaging the coordinates of all the selected particles. Subsequently,
458 the variables at the new particle i' are computed based on Taylor series as shown in
459 Equation (15) where h and k are the distances between the old particle and its new
460 (replacement) particle in the x and y directions respectively, and the required spatial
461 derivatives are obtained as explained in Section 2.2.

462 *A.2. Particle removal scheme*

463 Consider the example of large penetration of strip footing in soil (Case (B) in Section
464 3.5). As the strip footing moves down, soil particles not only move down but also
465 sideway due to Poisson's effect. As such, the vertical particle spacing decreases and the
466 horizontal spacing increases. For deep penetration, soil under the footing may be
467 serverely compressed against the fixed bottom boundary (e.g. a hard rock layer),
468 leading to two potential problems which may affect the numerical performance. First,
469 a smaller particle spacing vertically may require a smaller time step for numerical
470 stability based on the CFL condition (see Equation (14)). Second, the soil beneath the
471 footing is compressed (denser particles) while the soil outside the footing heaves (looser
472 particles). Hence, deep penetration of footing could cause large difference between the
473 particle spacings of soil in denser zone and soil in looser zone, which contributes to
474 irregular particle distribution at their interface. The issue can be resolved by the particle
475 repositioning scheme. Furthermore, since there are more sufficient particles than
476 necessary to accurately compute spatial derivatives of variables in the denser zone near
477 the fixed bottom boundary, some of the particles can be removed. In the study of
478 penetration of rigid strip footing in soil (Section 3.5), the criterion for triggering particle
479 removal is set as $L_1/L_2 < 0.8$, where L_1 is the average vertical particle spacing in the
480 denser zone and L_2 is that in the looser zone. When the above criterion is satisfied, some
481 particles in the denser zone will be removed. As a simple illustration in Figure A.2,
482 Row 1 contains soil particles in contact with the footing, Row 6 contains fixed particles
483 at the bottom fixed boundary, and Row 5 is the bottommost row of soil particles. The

484 particles in Row 5 under the footing will be removed when the above criterion is
485 satisfied. After particle removal, the remaining particles in the denser zone will be
486 adjusted by the particle repositioning scheme.

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491 REFERENCES

- 492 1. Donea J, Fasoli-Stella P, Giuliani S. Lagrangian and Eulerian finite element
493 techniques for transient fluid-structure interaction problems. *The 4th International
494 Conference on Structural Mechanics in Reactor Technology*, San Francisco, USA,
495 1977; Paper B1/2.
- 496 2. Belytschko T, Kennedy JM, Schoeberle DF. Quasi-Eulerian finite element
497 formulation for fluid-structure interaction. *Proceedings of Joint ASME/CSME
498 Pressure Vessels and Piping Conference*, Montreal, Canada, 1978; 78-PVP-60.
- 499 3. Hu Y, Randolph MF. A practical numerical approach for large deformation
500 problems in soil. *International Journal for Numerical and Analytical Methods in
501 Geomechanics* 1998; **22(5)**:327–350.
- 502 4. Tian Y, Cassidy MJ, Randolph MF, Wang D, Gaudin C. A simple implementation
503 of RITSS and its application in large deformation analysis. *Computers and
504 Geotechnics* 2014; **56**:160–167.

- 505 5. Qiu G, Grabe J. Numerical investigation of bearing capacity due to spudcan
506 penetration in sand overlying clay. *Canadian Geotechnical Journal* 2012;
507 **49(12)**:1393–1407.
- 508 6. Kencana EY, Haryono IS, Leung CF, Chow YK. Mass-gravity-scaling technique to
509 enhance computational efficiency of explicit numerical methods for quasi-static
510 problems. *Computers and Geotechnics* 2021; **133**:103999.
- 511 7. Wang D, Bienen B, Nazem M, Tian Y, Zheng J, Pucker T, Randolph MF. Large
512 deformation finite element analyses in geotechnical engineering. *Computers and*
513 *Geotechnics* 2015; **65**:104–114.
- 514 8. Oñate E, Idelsohn SR, Del Pin F, Aubry R. The particle finite element method-an
515 overview. *International Journal of Computational Methods* 2004; **1(02)**:267–307.
- 516 9. Monforte L, Arroyo M, Carbonell JM, Gens A. Numerical simulation of undrained
517 insertion problems in geotechnical engineering with the particle finite element
518 method (PFEM). *Computers and Geotechnics* 2017; **82**:144–156.
- 519 10. Cundall PA, Strack OD. A distinct element method for granular assemblies.
520 *Géotechnique* 1979; 29:47–65.
- 521 11. Sulsky D, Chen Z, Schreyer HL. A particle method for history-dependent materials.
522 *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering* 1994; **118**:179–196.
- 523 12. Lucy L. A numerical approach to testing the fission hypothesis. *Astronomical*
524 *Journal* 1977; **82**:1013–1024.

- 525 13. Gingold RA, Monaghan JJ. Smoothed particle hydrodynamics: theory and
526 application to nonspherical stars. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical*
527 *Society* 1977; **181**:375–389.
- 528 14. Libersky LD, Petschek AG. Smoothed particle hydrodynamics with strength of
529 materials. *Proceedings of the Next Free Lagrange Conference*, Moran, USA, 1991;
530 **395**:248–257.
- 531 15. Bui HH, Fukagawa R, Sako K, Ohno S. Lagrangian meshfree particles method
532 (SPH) for large deformation and failure flows of geomaterial using elastic-plastic
533 soil constitutive model. *International Journal for Numerical and Analytical*
534 *Methods in Geomechanics* 2008; **32**:1537–1570.
- 535 16. Monaghan JJ. Smoothed particle hydrodynamics. *Annual Review of Astronomy and*
536 *Astrophysics* 1992; **30**:543–574.
- 537 17. Koshizuka S, Oka Y, Tamako H. A particle method for calculating splashing of
538 incompressible viscous fluid. *International Conference, Mathematics and*
539 *Computations, Reactor Physics, and Environmental Analyses*, Oregon, USA, 1995;
540 **(2)**:1514–1521.
- 541 18. Koshizuka S, Oka Y. Moving-particle semi-implicit method for fragmentation of
542 incompressible fluid. *Nuclear Science and Engineering* 1996; **123(3)**:421–434.
- 543 19. Inazumi S, Kaneko M, Shigematsu Y, Shishido KI. Fluidity evaluation of
544 fluidisation treated soils based on the moving particle semi-implicit method.
545 *International Journal of Geotechnical Engineering* 2018; **12(4)**:325–336.

- 546 20. Kim KS, Lee JH. A simulation of soil dumping using moving particle semi-implicit
547 method. *Journal of Coastal Research* 2021; **114**:549–553.
- 548 21. Souto-Iglesias A, Macia F, Gonzalez LM, Cercos-Pita JL. On the consistency of
549 MPS. *Computer Physics Communications* 2013; **184(3)**:732–745.
- 550 22. Belytschko T, Krongauz Y, Organ D, Fleming M, Krysl P. Meshless methods: an
551 overview and recent developments. *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and*
552 *Engineering* 1996; **139**:3–47.
- 553 23. Luo M, Khayyer A, Lin P. Particle methods in ocean and coastal engineering.
554 *Applied Ocean Research* 2021; **114**:102734.
- 555 24. Koh CG, Gao M, Luo C. A new particle method for simulation of incompressible
556 free surface flow problems. *International Journal for Numerical Methods in*
557 *Engineering* 2012; **89(12)**:1582–1604.
- 558 25. Gao M, Koh CG, Luo M, Bai W. Modelling of breaking waves in tsunami and
559 sloshing waves by a new particle method, *5th International Symposium on Physics*
560 *of Fluids (ISPF5)*, Changbaishan, China, 2014; **34**:1460375.
- 561 26. Koh CG, Luo M, Gao M, Bai W. Modelling of liquid sloshing with constrained
562 floating baffle. *Computers and Structures* 2013; **122**:270–279.
- 563 27. Luo M, Koh CG, Gao M, Bai W. A particle method for two-phase flows with large
564 density difference. *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering*
565 2015; **103**:235–255.

- 566 28. Luo M, Koh CG, Bai W, Gao M. A particle method for two-phase flows with
567 compressible air pocket. *International Journal for Numerical Methods in*
568 *Engineering* 2016; **108**:695–721.
- 569 29. Li S. Numerical modelling of submarine landslides using consistent particle method.
570 *Ph.D. Thesis*, National University of Singapore, Singapore, 2017.
- 571 30. Chow YK, Li S, Koh CG. A particle method for simulation of submarine landslides
572 and mudflows. *The 29th International Ocean and Polar Engineering Conference*,
573 Hawaii, USA, 2019; ISOPE-I-19-594.
- 574 31. Courant R, Friedrichs K, Lewy H. On the partial difference equations of
575 mathematical physics. *IBM Journal* 1967; 215–234 (English translation of the 1928
576 German original).
- 577 32. Ryan TR. *Modern Regression Methods*. John Wiley and Sons: New York, 1997.
- 578 33. Koshizuka S, Nobe A, Oka Y. Numerical analysis of breaking waves using the
579 moving particle semi-implicit method. *International Journal for Numerical*
580 *Methods in Fluids* 1998; **26(7)**:751–769.
- 581 34. Viccione G, Bovolín V, Carratelli EP. Defining and optimizing algorithms for
582 neighbouring particle identification in SPH fluid simulations. *International Journal*
583 *for Numerical Methods in Fluids* 2008; **58**:625–638.
- 584 35. Macia F, Merino-Alonso PE, Souto-Iglesias A. On the truncated integral SPH
585 solution of the hydrostatic problem. *Computational Particle Mechanics* 2021;
586 **8**:325–336.

- 587 36. Libersky LD, Petschek AG, Carney TC, Hipp JR, Allahdadi FA. High strain
588 Lagrangian hydrodynamics, a three dimension SPH code for dynamic material
589 response. *Journal of Computational Physics* 1993; **109**:67–75.
- 590 37. Marrone S, Antuono M, Colagrossi A, Colicchio G, Le Touzé D, Graziani G. δ -
591 SPH model for simulation violent impact flows. *Computer Methods in Applied
592 Mechanics and Engineering* 2011; **200**:1526–1542.
- 593 38. Sinclair GB. Stress singularities in classical elasticity–I: removal, interpretation,
594 and analysis. *Applied Mechanics Review* 2004; **57**:251–297.
- 595 39. Meddaikar YM, Irisarri FX, Abdalla MM. Laminate optimization of blended
596 composite structures using a modified Shepard’s method and stacking sequence
597 tables. *Structural and Multidisciplinary Optimization* 2017; **55**:535–546.
- 598 40. Clough RW, Penzien J. *Dynamics of Structures*. McGraw-Hill: New York, 1975.
- 599 41. He LS. Improvement and application of smoothed particle hydrodynamics in
600 elastodynamics. *Ph.D. Thesis*, Durham University, Durham, 2015.
- 601 42. Swaddiwudhipong S, Liu ZS. Dynamic response of large strain elasto-plastic plate
602 and shell structure. *Thin Walled Structures* 1996; **26(4)**:223–239.
- 603 43. Liu ZS, Swaddiwudhipong S, Koh CG. Stress wave propagation in 1-D and 2-D
604 media using smoothed particle hydrodynamics method. *Structural Engineering and
605 Mechanics* 2002; **14(4)**:455–472.
- 606 44. Swegle JW, Attaway SW, Heinstein MW, Mello FJ, Hicks DL. An analysis of
607 smoothed particle hydrodynamics. *Sandia National Labs*, Albuquerque, New
608 Mexico, United States, 1994.

- 609 45. Liu MB, Liu GR. Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH): an overview and
610 recent developments. *Archives of Computational Methods in Engineering* 2010;
611 **17**:25–76.
- 612 46. *ABAQUS User Manual Version 6.14*. Simulia Inc., 2014.
- 613 47. Zienkiewicz OC, Valliappan S, King IP. Elasto-plastic solutions of engineering
614 problems: initial stress finite element approach. *International Journal for*
615 *Numerical Methods on Engineering* 1969; **1**:75–100.
- 616 48. Bui HH, Khoa HDV. Bearing capacity of shallow foundation by Smoothed Particle
617 Hydrodynamics (SPH) analysis. *Proceedings of the 2nd International Symposium*
618 *on Computational Geomechanics (COMGEO II)*, Cavat-Dubrovnik, USA, 2011;
619 457–468.
- 620 49. Qiu G, Henke S, Grabe J. Applications of Coupled Eulerian Lagrangian method to
621 geotechnical problems with large deformations. *Proceeding of SIMULIA Customer*
622 *Conference*, London, England, 2009; 420–435.
- 623 50. Jin YF, Yuan WH, Yin ZY, Cheng YM. An edge-based strain smoothing particle
624 finite element method for large deformation problems in geotechnical engineering.
625 *International Journal for Numerical and Analytical Methods in Geomechanics*
626 2020; **44**:923–941.
- 627 51. Hill R. *The Mathematical Theory of Plasticity*. The Clarendon Press: Oxford, 1950.

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Table 1. Numerical examples of CPM simulations

S/N	Problem	Material Model	Results for Comparison
1	Shock wave in a metal rod under compressive stress	Linearly elastic	Analytical and SPH (He, 2015)
2	Wave propagation in a rectangular plate under tensile stress	Linearly elastic	FEM (Swaddiwudhipong and Liu, 1996); SPH (Liu et al., 2002)
3	Loading, unloading and reloading of soil under reversing velocity	(A) Von Mises (inscribed) (B) Drucker-Prager (inscribed) with associated flow rule	FEM (Abaqus)
4	Bearing capacity of rigid strip footing on soil stratum	Drucker-Prager (inscribed) with (A) associated flow rule (B) non-associated flow rule	FEM (Abaqus); SPH (Bui and Khoa, 2011)
5	Penetration of rigid strip footing in soil stratum for two penetration depths: (A) $D = 0.25B$ (B) $D = 2.0B$	(A) Von Mises (inscribed) (B) Von Mises (circumscribed)	(A) Analytical (Hill, 1950); FEM (Qiu et al., 2009); SPFEM (Jin et al., 2020) (B) FEM results (Kencana, 2021)

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Figure 1. Predictor-corrector time stepping scheme in CPM

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637 Figure 2. Reference particle i and neighbour particles j within influence radius $r_e =$

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$3.1L_0$

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Figure 3. 1-D magnesium rod under compressive stress

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Figure 4. Velocity distribution along rod at $t = 1.2 \times 10^{-4}$ s in comparison with

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analytical solution – 251 particles used in SPH and CPM

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Figure 5. Time history of stress magnitude at fixed end of rod in comparison with

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analytical solution – 251 particles used in SPH and CPM

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654 Figure 6. Time history of stress magnitude at fixed end of rod – RKC-SPH (left) and

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CPM (right) in comparison with analytical solution

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Figure 7. Steel plate under tensile stress

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666 Figure 8. CPM model with 51×26 material particles for wave propagation in plate

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669 Figure 9. Time history of horizontal displacement at middle of plate (Point B)

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671 Figure 10. Time history of horizontal displacement at middle of right edge (Point C)

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674 Figure 11. Time history of horizontal stress (σ_{xx}) at middle of left edge (Point A)

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Figure 12. Time history of horizontal stress (σ_{xx}) at middle of plate (Point *B*)

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Figure 13. Soil under applied velocity with reversing amplitudes

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681 Figure 14. Soil compression using von Mises model: σ_{yy} vs u_y at midpoint of top

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boundary

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685 Figure 15. Soil compression using Drucker-Prager model: σ_{yy} vs u_y at midpoint of top
686 boundary

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690 Figure 16. Schematic diagram of strip footing bearing capacity problem

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692 Figure 17. Bearing curve of strip footing based on Drucker-Prager model with

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associated flow rule

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695 Figure 18. Bearing curve of strip footing based on Drucker-Prager model with non-
 696 associated flow rule

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699 Figure 19. Schematic diagram of strip footing penetration problem ($D = 0.25B$)

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Figure 20. Bearing curve of strip footing penetration problem ($D = 0.25B$)

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704 Figure 21. CPM particle distribution at $D = 0.25B$ (solid line: initial soil profile)

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707 Figure 22. Soil profile near footing at $D = 0.25B$ (black line: initial soil profile)

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710 Figure 23. Velocity vectors and slip surface by CPM at $D = 0.25B$ (solid line: soil
711 profile, dashed line: slip surface)

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714 Figure 24. Schematic diagram of strip footing penetration problem ($D = 2.0B$)

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Figure 25. Bearing curve of strip footing penetration problem ($D = 2.0B$)

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Figure 26. CPM particle distribution at $D = 2.0B$ (solid line: initial soil profile)

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721 Figure 27. Soil profile near footing at $D = 2.0B$ (black line: initial soil profile)

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724 Figure 28. Velocity vectors and slip surface by CPM at $D = 2.0B$ (solid line: soil

725 profile, dashed line: slip surface)

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- Reference particle
- Particle selected
- Particle not selected

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Figure A.1. Selection of particle pairs for particle repositioning

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Figure A.2. Removal of particles in dense zone beneath footing

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